

The Effect of Service Quality, Price, Promotion, Brand Image and Trust in Customer Satisfaction of Soekarno Hatta Airport Railway

Roy Darwis Siagian, Prof. Dr. Ngadino Surip MS
Mercu Buana University, Jakarta

Abstract:- This research aims to analyze the influence of service quality, price, promotion, brand image and trust in consumer satisfaction. The phenomenon that occurs today is the development of high transportation the importance of maintaining consumer satisfaction, which occurs is the development of the number of visitors in soekarnohatta city that continues to rise along with other transportation which is various kinds of therefore the importance of the soekarnahatta airport fire kerati maintains consumer satisfaction because consumer satisfaction can cause some impact and can also be used as a reference related to the amount of income, And the profit that will be received by the company if the company is unable to maintain consumer satisfaction does not rule out the possibility that the income obtained also decreases. The object of this study is the consumer of the airport train soekarnahatta, and the number of sampel specified is 220 respondents using the calculation method based on the heir formula multiplied by 5. Purposive sampling method, data collection method using kusioner, and data analysis using *Partial Least Square* (PLS). The results of the study found that the quality of service affects customer satisfaction, price affects customer satisfaction, promotion affects brand image, and trust in consumer satisfaction.

Keywords:- Quality of service, Price, Promotion, Brand image, Trust, and Customer satisfaction.

I. INTRODUCTION

In this modern era, people have diverse activities and to fulfill these activities the community needs transportation as a supporting tool or tool in carrying out its activities.

To win the competition, the company must be able to provide satisfaction to its consumers, one example is the transportation services company. According to existing data dibandarasoekarnohatta.com the number of passengers in 2016 reached 45,064,449 and in 2017 increased to 48,074,549 this increase in passenger numbers is predicted to continue to increase in the following year with an increase of 8% in each know. Many kinds of land vehicle transportation to the airport such as damri, online taxi, *conventional taxi* and just inaugurated railink airport train on January 2, 2018. Soekarno Hatta airport train is also expected to help passengers to Soekarno Hatta Airport and from Soekarno Hatta Airport to various places in Jakarta, Bogor, Depok, Tangerang, and Bekasi.

Airport trains are faced with the tight competition of existing transportation services, companies need to pay close attention to consumer behavior and what factors affect consumers in order to create consumer satisfaction. According to Kotler and Armstrong (2015) promotion aims to influence people to participate in purchases, promotion also aims to motivate people to buy a company's products or services, as well as being a means to build and measure customer satisfaction. Brand image with consumer satisfaction has an influence. Brand image is an *image* or something that sticks in the minds of consumers. The better the perception in the minds of consumers of the company's brand image, the higher consumer satisfaction. According to the results of the pre-survey above, it can be concluded that consumer satisfaction many choose to use airport trains influenced by the most answer from the statement is the price of 47 respondents, the quality of service 46 and the promotion of 44 respondents. With a price of 47 : 50 x 100 = 94%, Service quality 46 : 50 x 100 = 92%, Promotion 44 : 50 x 100 = 88%, Image 40 : 50 x 100 = 80%, Trust 37 : 50 x 100 = 74%. Consumer satisfaction can cause several impacts and can also be used as a reference related to the amount of revenue, and profits that will be received by the company.

The future will come because it will be done.

Quality of service is very important in the service transportation sector if the quality of service is decreasing, it will result in a decrease in consumers that makes the longer the company's income decreases.

II. LITERATURE

A. Marketing Management

Marketing management occurs when at least one party of the pontesial exchange thinks of a way to get a response from the other party in accordance with the desired. The definition reduces that marketing management is a process that involves analyzing, planning, implementing, and controlling goods, services, and ideas that depend on exchanges and with the aim of generating satisfaction for the parties involved. Marketing management affects the level, time and composition of demand so that the company achieves its goals. (Kotler and Keller 2013).

B. Service Marketing

FandyTjiptono (2016:4) defines "Service can be viewed as a system consisting of two main components, namely service operations that are often not tampak or unknown to the customer (back office or backstage) and service delivery that usually looks (visible) or known to customers (often called front office or frontstage)".

C. Quality of service

(Tjiptono and Chandra, 2011) states that quality of service is a function of consumer expectations in pre-purchase, in the process of providing quality received and on the quality of output received. So that the quality of service can be interpreted as an effort to meet the needs and desires of customers and the accuracy of delivery in balancing customer expectations. There are two factors that affect the quality of services, namely expected service and perceived service or quality of services expected and quality of services received or felt. The quality of service according to (Tjiptono, 2011) is influenced by five dimensions of service quality, namely *Reliability* (reliability), *Responsiveness* (responsiveness), *Assurance* (assurance), *Empathy* (empathy), and *Tangible* (physical evidence).

D. Price

According to Kotler and Armstrong in Permana et al (2018) price is defined as something given or sacrificed to obtain a service or product. According to (Kotler and Keller, 2012) states that the price dimension consists of price affordability, price conformity with quality, price conformity with benefits, and price competitiveness.

E. Brand Image

Brand imagery can be defined as their name, terms, signs, symbols, or combinations intended to identify the goods and services of a single seller or group of sellers and to distinguish them from competitors. Tjiptono brand image dimensions (2015) state that there are several dimensions that make up the brand image, including company image, product image, and prestige user image.

F. Understanding Promotion

Promotion is also information to the act of redemption and purchase or one-way information tools for someone. According to Stanton in Sunyoto (2012) "Promotion is an element in a company's marketing mix that is used to inform, persuade and remind about a company's products" whereas according to Kotler and Keller (2013) Sales promotion is a core ingredient in marketing campaigns, consisting of a collection of incentive tools, as large as short-term ones designed to stimulate faster purchases of certain products by consumers. According to Kotler and Armstrong (2012), the promotional mix consists of 5 (five) promotional tools, namely *Advertising*, *Sales promotion*, *Direct Marketing*, *Personal Selling*, and *Public Relations*.

G. Belief

Customer trust arises indicated by a credibility gained from other parties because it has the skills that are required to perform a task. Customer trust can also be gained for doing the best thing to the other party through a relationship. (Hermawan, 2011) The level of customer trust can be measured through several factors including honesty in transacting, company responsibility to customers and much more. Zikmud in Soegoto (2013) has dimensions including Trust in companies, Trust in services or products, and Trust in brands

H. Consumer Satisfaction

According to Tjiptono (2015:146), "consumer satisfaction is the feeling of pleasure or disappointment of someone who arises after comparing the perception of the performance (results) of a product with his expectations". So according to some of these definitions, it can be concluded that satisfaction is a result of a comparison between expectations and performance obtained, therefore research is needed to determine consumer expectations so that the company can meet those expectations. measurement of satisfaction expressed by Fornel in Tjiptono quoted (Indah, 2014), namely, Overall satisfaction, Confirmation of expectation, and Comperation to ideal

III. THINK THE THOUGHTS

Fig. 1: Frame of Mind

Based on previous theories and research, the research hypothesis can be described as follows:

- Hypothesis 1: Quality of Service has a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction.
- Hypothesis 2: Price has a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction.
- Hypothesis 3: Brand image has a positive effect and significant consumer satisfaction.
- Hypothesis 4: Promotion has a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction.
- Hypothesis 5: Trust has a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction.

IV. RESEARCH METHODS

The research method used in this research is a method of quantitative analysis, which is research that emphasizes its analysis on data or numerical numbers obtained by statistical methods. Sugiyono (2010: 13) suggests quantitative research can be interpreted as a research method based on the philosophy of positivism, used to examine a particular population or sample, data collection using research instruments, quantitative or statistical data analysis, with the aim of testing hypotheses. In the study conducted a Validity Test of each variable, reliability test, and matrix correlation test.

A. Population and Sample

In this study selected the research population is railink airport rail consumers. However, it is not known how many populations in the study so using the number of indicators multiplied by 5 Hair *et al* in Prawira (2010). In this study the population used is a consumer of Railink airport train. In determining the number of samples in the study is five multiplied by the number of indicators. So, five is multiplied by 44. So the number of samples in this study was 220.

B. Discriminant Validity

	Brand image	Price	Trust	Consumer satisfaction	Quality of service	Promotion
Brand image	0.721					
Price	0.220	0.727				
Belief	0.366	0.368	0.743			
Consumer satisfaction	0.525	0.628	0.659	0.870		
Quality of service	0.401	0.470	0.560	0.594	0.716	
Promotion	0.459	0.480	0.560	0.635	0.640	0.736

Table 1: Discriminant Validity Results (FornellLarcker)

The loading factor value for each indicator of each variable already has a loading factor value that is not the largest compared to the loading value if it is associated with other variables. This means that each variable has a good discriminant validity where some variables still have a meter that is highly correlated with other constructs.

C. Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

Variable	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Brand image	0.520
Price	0.528
Belief	0.707
Consumer Satisfaction	0.757
Kualtias service	0.512
Promotion	0.542

It can be seen that the results of composite reliability and cronbach alpha tests show satisfactory values, i.e. all variables have a reliable because all latent variable values have composite reliability values and cronbach alpha ≥ 0.70 . So it can be concluded that, the questionnaire used as a research tool has been reliable or consistent.

B. Data Collection Techniques

In this study, data collection techniques were carried out by distributing questionnaires to Railink airport rail consumers. The data collected is primary data and secondary data.

C. Data Analysis Methods

In this study, the authors used quantitative descriptive analysis, aided by IBM's SPSS Statistic 23 and Partial Least Square (PLS) software. To facilitate research on the data collected.

V. PENENELITIAN RESULTS

Based on the results of data processing showed that of 220 respondents there were 132 male respoden by 60%... 26 - 30 years as many as 109 respondents with a presentation of 49.4%, . It can be concluded in this study mostly aged 26-30 years because we can know that the age of airport train consumers is already entering the productive age. Furthermore, the characteristics of respondents based on work there are 37 respoden working as civil servants, private employees as many as 123 respondents, students or students.

A. Evaluation of Measurement (Outer Model)

The result of the Outer Model modification that all indicators have met convergent validity because it has a loading factor value above 0.50. Thus, all modified indicators are declared valid all.

D. R Square Value

Above it can be concluded that the model on the consumer satisfaction variable is 0.585 or 58.5% which means consumer satisfaction can be explained by variables in the model, namely service quality, brand image,

promotion, trust, and price. The remaining 41.5% was explained by other variables not studied in this model.

Look at the significance of the hypothesis by looking at the parameter coefficient value and the statistical significance value t in the algorithm bootstrapping report.

E. Hypothesis Testing Results

	Original Sample	T Statistic (O/STDEV)	P Values
Brand image > Consumer satisfaction	0.188	3.773	0.000
Price > Consumer satisfaction	0.145	3.232	0.001
Trust > consumer satisfaction	0.176	3.374	0.001
Quality of service > Customer satisfaction	0.266	4.900	0.000
Promotion > Customer Satisfaction	0.290	5.252	0.000

Table 3: Hypothesis Testing Results

VI. DISCUSSION

A. Influence of brand image on consumer satisfaction

Based on hypothesis tests on this study, it shows results that brand image has a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction. It is significant because, the statistical T value > T table (3,773 > 1.96) or we can know that T calculates > of T table is significant because the probabilitas value < 0.05. This means that the increasing brand image on airport trains can increase consumer satisfaction. This result can be interpreted if the brand image owned through each indicator is always improved such as being able to provide guarantees on time it will make the brand image continue to be good which has an impact on consumer satisfaction itself. The results of the hypothesis test in this study are supported by Zahra (2017) who said that brand image has a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction, and according to Kurnia (2019) who said that brand image has a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction.

B. Effect of Price on Consumer Satisfaction

Based on hypothesis tests on this study, it shows results that the statistical T is greater than the T table (3,232 > 1.96) or we can know that T calculates > of the T table is significant because the probabilitas value < 0.05. Thus the results of hypothesis tests in this study showed price had a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction. The results of the hypothesis test in this study can be interpreted if the price felt by consumers in accordance with what they spend will also increase the satisfaction of these consumers, because they feel a good effect according to how much money they spend. The results of the hypothesis test in this study are supported by research conducted by Sulisty (2018) which said prices have a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction, Tikarina (2019) which said that prices have a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction, and Kurnia (2019) which says that prices have a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction.

C. Influence of Trust on Consumer Satisfaction

Based on hypothesis tests on this study, it shows results that the statistical T is greater than the T table ($3,374 > 1.96$) or we can know that T calculates $>$ of the T table is significant because the probabilitas value < 0.05 . Thus the results of hypothesis tests in this study showed confidence to have a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction. If the relevant parties can increase and provide good trust through every indicator that exists, it will also increase consumer satisfaction. The results of the hypothesis test in this study are supported by research conducted by Paramita and Febrianto (2018) who said that trust has a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction, Wedyani (2019) who said that trust has a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction.

D. Effect of Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction

Based on hypothesis tests on this study, it shows results that the statistical T is greater than the T table ($4,900 > 1.96$) or we can know that T calculates $>$ of T table is significant because the probabilitas value < 0.05 . Thus the results of hypothesis tests in this study showed the quality of service had a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction. If the relevant party can improve the service in a way that is able to serve consumers well and able to communicate well, it will increase the satisfaction of the consumer. The results of the hypothesis test in this study are supported by research conducted by Kurnia (2019) which said that the quality of service has a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction, Fahrudin (2018) who said that the quality of service has a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction.

E. Effect of Promotion on Consumer Satisfaction

Based on hypothesis tests on this study, it shows results that the statistical T is greater than the T table ($5,252 > 1.96$) or we can know that T calculates $>$ of the T table is significant because the probabilitas value < 0.05 . Thus the results of hypothesis tests in this study showed that promotion had a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction. If the relevant parties can improve and utilize existing promotional media through the internet and social media, it will increase consumer satisfaction itself because consumers are facilitated in getting information about airport trains and other promos. The results of the hypothesis test in this study are supported by research conducted by Hanaysah (2017) which said that promotion has a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction, Rahayu (2015) which said that promotion has a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction.

F. Correlation Matrix

Hasil from the correlation matrix is known to be a service quality variable that has a strong dimension influence that is foury to the dimension of overall satisfaction consumer satisfaction with a value of 0.772, then from the results of the data above found the largest correlation in the dimension of price in the price variable with the dimension of confirmation of expectation on the consumer satisfaction variable with a value of 0.836 which means very strong. Based on the matrix test of the correlation of variable brand image there is a strong

correlation with the value of 0.749 user images with the dimension of confirmation of expectation on consumer satisfaction variables, correlation results are also obtained strong values in the direct marketing dimension in promotional variables with a value of 0.611 in the overall satisfaction dimension on consumer satisfaction, the last based on the results of matrix correlation tests obtained results that the dimension of trust in the company has a correlation. strong against the dimension of comperation to the ideal that exists in consumer satisfaction variables.

VII. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

A. Conclusion

- Based on the results of the hypothesis test, the cauldron of services has a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction with an influential dimension that is the foury dimension related to the overall satisfaction dimension with a strong correlation coefficient.
- Based on the results of the price hypothesis test, the price hypothesis has a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction. There is also an influential dimension that is the price sticking with the dimension of confirmation of expectation with a very strong correlation coefficient.
- Based on the results of the test hypothesis brand image positively and significantly on consumer satisfaction with an influential dimension that is the dimension of the user image related to the dimension of confirmation of expectation with a strong correlation coefficient.
- Based on the results of the promotion hypothesis test, the promotion hypothesis has a positive and significant effect on consumer satisfaction with an influential dimension, namely the direct marketing dimension related to the overall satisfaction dimension with a strong correlation coefficient.
- Based on the results of the belief hypothesis test, the confidence positively and significantly affects consumer satisfaction with an influential dimension, namely the trust dimension of the company related to the dimension of comperation to ideal with a strong correlation coefficient.

B. Suggestion

a) Suggestionthe company

- Based on the results of the test and the conclusions obtained, on the variable quality of service to consumer satisfaction with the strongest dimensions, namely foury that have two indicators in it, namely the first to understand the will and needs of consumers by re-evaluating the overall service they have so that the results of evaluations that have been done can make a benchmark in the future such as train departure, and the fastilitas of other support in the field. The second suggestion communicates well the advice that can be given to the company to conduct training activities clearly by using experts in their fields so that communication between consumers and consumers

there is no misscommunication so that later the creation of consumer satisfaction.

- Based on the results of the test and the conclusions obtained, on the price variable to consumer satisfaction with the strongest dimension is the price satuness that has one indicator in it, namely by re-evaluating the existing price with its competitors and then providing a bundling price where the price given is included with the cost of transportation that they go next.
- Based on the results of the test and the conclusions obtained, on the variable brand image to consumer satisfaction with the strongest dimension is the image of the company that has three indicators in it, namely in the first way to create good popularity advice to managers to cooperate with several community friends train, because the community is able to provide a good image to the company, The second suggestion that can be taken into consideration to the company so that the company can be trusted is to use influencers instagram platform, youtube, and or tiktok so that later useful to the company's image in the address of consumers, the third suggestion to the company that can be taken into consideration is to cooperate with several travel agent platforms such as Traveloka and Tiket.com.
- Based on the results of the test and the conclusions obtained, on the variable promotion to consumer satisfaction with the strongest dimension is direct marketing by having two indicators in it, namely the first social media, advice that can be given advice to companies related to these indicators is by utilizing social media that they have by providing related promotional information such as discount programs that companies have so that later the promotion is Companies can be achieved to consumers, the second suggestion with digital brochure indicators is by utilizing digital platforms such as imooji and quancast.
- Based on the results of the test and the conclusions obtained, on the variable confidence in consumer satisfaction with the strongest dimension is trusting the company by having one indicator in it, namely advice that can be taken into consideration by the company by making testimonials on the web, social media that they have such as videos or photos.

b) Suggestion for The Next Researcher

Consumer satisfaction can be explained by variables in the model, namely service quality, brand image, price, promotion, and trust while the rest is explained by other variables not studied in this model, and suggestions for researchers to further be able to re-develop variables and indicators that have not been used in this study such as this study such as word of mouth, and ease that can affect consumer satisfaction. In addition, for researchers who will Doing research in the same field and using this thesis as a reference, then it needs to be reviewed because it does not rule out the possibility of statements that are not appropriate,

because researchers feel there are still many shortcomings and limitations in completing this thesis.

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